

MODERN MODEL OF EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE BASED ON THE ANDRAGOGIC APPROACH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Andragogika - bu pedagogikaning sohasi bo'lib, katta yoshlilar ta'limi, muammolarini, amaliyotini metodolgik asoslarni o'rganuvchi tizimdir. Katta yoshli o'rganuvchiular o'z-o'zini taxlil qiladi, o'z-o'zini sinaydi. O'z - o'zini baholay oladi xatosini o'zi tuzata oladi. Kasbiy ta'lim, mustqail ta'lim, madaniy- estetik faoliyat shakllarda namoyon bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Andragogika, pedagogika sohasi, kattalar ta'limi, muammolar, insonshunoslik, kattalar ta'limi amaliyoti, metodologik asoslar, xayot yo'li, tamoyillar, vositalar, rivojlantiruvchi, ijtimoiylashtiruvchi, moslashtiruvchi, mavqe, o'z-o'zini taxlil, o'z-o'zini sinash, refleksiya, o'z-o'zini baxolash, o'z-o'zini tuzatish, jarayon, kasbiy ta'lim, mustaqil ta'lim, madaniy-estetik faoliyat, ma'naviy yuksalish, shakl, funktsiya, modellashtirish.

Аннотация

Андрогогика — область педагогики, система, изучающая методологические основы образования взрослых, проблемы и практику. Взрослые учащиеся анализируют себя и проверяют себя. Он может оценивать себя и исправлять свои ошибки. Профессиональное образование, самостоятельное образование, культурно-эстетическая деятельность проявляются в формах.

Ключевые слова: андрогогика, область педагогики, образование взрослых, проблемы, гуманитарные науки, практика образования взрослых, методологические основы, образ жизни, принципы, инструменты, развитие, социализация, адаптация, позиция, самоанализ, самоанализ, рефлексия. самооценка, самокоррекция, процесс, профессиональное образование, самостоятельное образование, культурно-эстетическая деятельность, духовное возвышение, форма, функция, моделирование.

ABSTRACT

Andragogy is a field of pedagogy, a system that studies the methodological foundations of adult education, problems, and practice. Adult learners analyze themselves and test themselves. He can self-evaluate and correct his mistakes. Vocational education, independent education, cultural-aesthetic activities are manifested in forms.

Key words: andragogy, field of pedagogy, adult education, problems, humanities, practice of adult education, methodological foundations, way of life, principles, tools, developing, socializing, adapting, position, self-analysis, self-examination, reflection, self-evaluation, self-correction, process, professional education, independent education, cultural-aesthetic activity, spiritual elevation, form, function, modeling.

An adult is a person who has a constructive role of social importance and feels responsible for his life.

(G.G. Darkenwald and S.B. Merriem)

In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education..." (23.09.2020) "Education and education of adults" was included as a form of education.

"Adult education and training is a central component of lifelong learning and includes all forms of education and training aimed at ensuring the participation of adults in society and work, as well as the whole range of formal, non-formal and informal learning processes. ". (Article 19)

Andragogy - professional development, possibilities of distance education in teaching adults, public universities, women's education, forms and technologies of adult education, education of older readers, educational tourism, mastering pedagogical andragogy in the organization of the pedagogical process requires. The history of the development of andragogic adult education and the theoretical practice of andragogy, adult education in the continuing education system are components of pedagogical andragogy. That is why this subject is of special importance in the formation of skills and qualifications of pedagogical andragogy in future pedagogues.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE SCIENCE OF ANDRAGOGY.

Goals and tasks of andragogy

- General understanding of the science of andragogy.
- Specific aspects of adult education.
- Requirements, problems for studying the science of andragogy, the essence of andragogy in the system of humanities.
- Theoretical and methodological bases of andragogic activity, principles, methods and tools of training and education of a person throughout his life.
- Andragogy - as a science that develops the life of adults, adapts it to the social environment and enriches it with education.

The concept of "Andragogy" as a scientific term was introduced to the science in 1833 by the German pedagogue-historian A. Kapp. If it is interpreted side by side with the word "Pedagogy", it becomes clear that its origin consists of Greek words (andros-man, man; agogein-to lead). Literally translated, andragogy is "to lead an adult". This term is related to the pedagogical reality and refers to leadership through teaching. Different areas of andragogy can be considered:

- field of scientific knowledge;
- field of social practice;
- field of educational subject;

In order to think about the relevance of andragogy to the field of scientific knowledge, it is necessary to determine the following:

- the subject he is studying;
- system of concepts explaining the subject;
- the main principles and methods that create the basis for scientific knowledge and renewal.

Accordingly, andragogic knowledge finds its expression in the place and structure of modern sciences. Mastering andragogy in the field of social practice, based on the essence of adult education, involves the clarification of professional direction, knowledge, skills, competences and valuable attitudes. To understand andragogy as an academic discipline, its expert it is important to be able to determine the scope and capabilities of the training system. Andragogy, a relatively new field of scientific knowledge, is experiencing a revival. The closeness of the terms "Pedagogy" and "Andragogy" has been the cause of various discussions

and debates for many years. While the concept of "Andragogy" is close to the field of pedagogy, one should not forget the specific aspects of teaching adults. Due to these contradictions, the main place of the science of andragogy has not been determined

Principles of andragogic education model

1. The adult learner strives for self-expression, achievement, self-management and sees himself as
2. An adult learner strives for self-expression, achievement, self-control and sees himself as such.
3. An adult learner has a lot of life, household, professional experience, and this can serve as an important resource for his and his colleagues' education.
4. An adult learner studies to solve an important life issue and to achieve a specific goal.
5. An adult learner wants to immediately apply the knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired in the educational process.
6. The educational activity of an adult learner largely depends on time, place, social, household factors, which either hinder or create conditions for the educational process.
7. The educational process of an adult learner is based on the equal cooperation of the learner and the teacher in all its stages: planning, organization, evaluation and to some extent making changes.
8. Adults also want to be involved in choosing topics and setting questions for discussion based on their experiences and what they are having trouble with.

The type of education is divided into two: pedagogy and andragogy. Children of pedagogic school age up to school age are taught the secrets of the whole world - industry, scientific innovations. It is taught using a complete program based on a specific system. Offline or online teaching is chosen by the teacher and lessons are held under strict supervision of the student. In Andragogy, adults choose their own forms of education. They freely choose according to their circumstances. For example, distance learning is carried out with a learner moderator, depending on his/her own time and capabilities, and conducting the lesson in a complex or easy way depending on the needs of the adult learner.

Research shows that the motivation factor for successful study is often stronger than the intelligence factor. It is important to support learner motivation in making the learning process enjoyable. For this reason, it is necessary to take into account the methods and approaches to formation, development, and maintenance of motivation, and organize lessons and educational materials.

First, the presented texts, audio-visual materials, tasks and lessons should be suitable for the learner's interests.

Second, the teacher should allow older learners to evaluate the performance of tasks and their needs should play a primary role.

The third important thing is the humor in the lessons, in addition to the subject of the lesson, such as music, extracurricular components are features that increase students' enthusiasm for learning. As additional activities, we can include not only humor or entertainment activities, but also organization of competitions among students according to the purpose of the course, for example, poster presentations, video presentations, project work, organization of project work in groups, etc. Now let's summarize our thoughts above.

Pedagogy for children

Andragogy for adult learners

What do I learn?

YOU know what you need

YOU SHOULD TEACH ME

*I do not have **experience**, I believe what you tell me.*

I need to learn SCIENCE

I must study

I know what I want

I have a wish, but YOU have to help me

YOU should consider my experience

I want to acquire knowledge that will help me solve my problems

I ... need

Summary

People of different ages learn differently. Adults have their own learning characteristics, which should be taken into account when organizing courses for them. Adults prefer to solve specific problems and study independently, for them knowledge directly related to their work and life becomes relevant.

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